

Water

Perspectives on Nonpoint Source Pollution

PERSPECTIVES ON NONPOINT SOURCE POLLUTION

Proceedings of a National Conference

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FOREWORD

A cursory scan of this book will tell the reader that this is no ordinary proceedings of a conference. Indeed, the papers published here reflect a conference that was neither ordinary nor routine. These papers are very dissimilar—in length, in format, in tone. But they are alike in one vital way: each represents a slightly different perspective on the problem of nonpoint source pollution of our Nation's water.

And that was the intent: to gather together all those organizations and individuals concerned with this problem and to draw from them the most practical ways to deal with it.

As Assistant Administrator for Water at the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency, Jack Ravan conceived this conference as an integral part of the Agency's approach to nonpoint source pollution. The other three components are discussed in this volume: ASIWPCA's survey of the States (being completed this fall); the Federal Nonpoint Source Task Force (which concluded its initial policy and strategy development at the end of 1984); and the Chesapeake Bay study now underway by the National Association of Conservation Districts.

Ravan's instructions for this conference were fourfold: (1) focus on drawing information from everybody involved with the problem; (2) find out how people throughout the country, at the local level, perceive the nonpoint source problem and how they believe it should be handled; (3) make the information flow from the grass roots upward—the Federal role was to listen and learn and exchange information, not to dominate; and (4) make it practical.

The conference steering committee took this charge very seriously, designing a structure that stimulated this flow of information. The program committee fleshed it out, using both submitted and invited presentations.

The result was essentially a practical dialog. Of course, it cannot be fully covered in these presentations, but they will serve to remind participants of the equally valuable informal exchanges that took place during the week in Kansas City.

Four basic themes evolved as the conference developed.

Practical, affordable solutions not imposed by Federal authority but worked out at the local level was the message of the keynoter, Congressman Pat Roberts of Kansas' First District.

The knowledge exists, participants reiterated throughout the sessions. Putting it to work is the next step.

Nonpoint source pollution is best solved at the local level, concluded Robert I. Broadbent, Assistant Secretary for Water and Science at the Department of the Interior, as he moderated the closing plenary session. Broadbent's conclusion was drawn from two days of listening to sessions and to individuals—and is repeated throughout this volume. Discussions of new State programs in Missouri and Maryland reinforce this belief.

Cooperation is the key. Ravan sounded that note at the opening plenary—and it continued to be apparent throughout the conference. Nearly 40 organizations came together to cosponsor this conference—many others were represented among the attendees. In the real-life capitals of this country, these organizations often find themselves at odds; many had never talked over their mutual concerns.

This conference certainly began such a dialog. And, as a session chairman, Roger Bollinger, observed, there was evident a willingness to talk, a maturity “that may allow us to truly begin solving our water quality problems.”

If a mature optimism and diversity of perspective were its hallmarks, then this conference's true success can be measured only by how we move forward from here. We have the information—in this volume, from this conference—but the communication established must translate into working together to improve the quality of our Nation's waters.

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